

Improving the foundations of the scientific record: data citation and publication by the NERC data centres

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The Scientific Method

A key part of the scientific method is that it should be reproducible – other people doing the same experiments in the same way should get the same results.

Unfortunately observational data is not reproducible (unless you have a time machine!)

The way data is organised and archived is crucial to the reproducibility of science and our ability to test conclusions.

This is often the only part of the process that anyone other than the originating scientist sees.

We want to change this.

<http://www.mrsaverettsclassroom.com/bio/2-scientific-method.php>

Who are we and why do we care about data?

The UK's Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) funds six data centres which between them have responsibility for the long-term management of NERC's environmental data holdings.

We deal with a variety of environmental measurements, along with the results of model simulations.

As part of the NERC Science Information Strategy (SIS) several projects have been created to provide the framework for NERC to work more closely and effectively with its scientific communities in delivering data and information management services.

One of these is the Data Citation and Publication Project

Historically speaking...

... data was hard to capture, but could be (relatively) easily published in image or table format

But now...

there's simply too much information associated with everything we need to know about a scientific event

- whether that's an observation, simulation, development of a theory, or any combination of these.

Data always has been the foundation of scientific progress – without it, we can't test any of our assertions, or reproduce our findings!

Suber cells and mimosa leaves. Robert Hooke, Micrographia, 1665

The Data Deluge

“the amount of data generated worldwide...is growing by 58% per year; in 2010 the world generated 1250 billion gigabytes of data”

The Digital Universe Decade – Are You Ready?
IDCC White Paper, May 2010

A lot of people are creating a lot of data, and we're only going to get more of it.

If this is a data deluge – time to start building arks!

Figure 1: The Digital Universe 2009 – 2020
Growing by a Factor of 44

*Zettabyte = 1 trillion gigabytes

Will sharing our data help?

Benefits of sharing:

- Ability to discover and reuse data which has already been collected
- Avoid redundant data collection
- Save time and money
- Provide opportunities for collaboration.

Research funders are keen to encourage data sharing.

For the most part, scientists are happy to share other scientists' data, but...

Knowledge is power!

Data may mean the difference between getting a grant and not.

There is (currently) no universally accepted mechanism for data creators to obtain academic credit for their dataset creation efforts.

Creators (understandably) prefer to hold the data until they have extracted all the possible publication value they can.

This behaviour comes at a cost for the wider scientific community.

Reframing “sharing” as “publication” might encourage scientists to be more open with their data.

Why do we want to cite and publish data?

- Pressure from the UK government to make all data from publicly funded research available to the public for free.
 - Scientists still want to receive attribution and credit for their work
 - General public want to know what the scientists are doing (Climategate...)
- Research funders want reassurance that they're getting value for money from their funding
 - Relies on peer-review of science publications (well established) and data (not done yet!)
- Allows the wider research community to find and use datasets outside their immediate domain, confident that the data is of reasonable quality
- From a strict data-centric point of view, citation and publication provides an extra incentive for scientists to submit their data to us in appropriate formats and with full metadata!

Data Citation and Publication Project Aims

- To implement publication and citation of datasets held within the NERC data centres.
- To increase NERC's influence on work to provide and cite data outputs from scientific work in similar ways to scientific papers.
- To demonstrate to the NERC community that data citation and publication is both personally and scientifically advantageous.
- To form partnerships with other organisations with the same goal of data publication to exploit common activities and achieve a wider community buy-in. To this end, project team members are involved with both the SCOR/IODE/MBL WHOI Library Data Publication Working Group, the CODATA-ICSTI Task Group on Data Citation Standards and Practises and the DataCite Working Group on Criteria for Datacentres.

- **Provide a reward to scientists who create data for all their efforts in putting their data in one of our data centres.**

The Not-So-Secret life of a PI.

“Publishing” versus “publishing” and “Open” versus “Closed”

We draw a clear distinction between:

publishing/serving = making available for consumption (e.g. on the web), and

Publishing = publishing after some formal process which adds value for the consumer:

- e.g. PloS ONE type review, or
- EGU journal type public review, or
- More traditional peer review.

AND

- provides commitment to persistence

Published
↑
Not Published

We want to:

Encourage scientists to move away from storing their data on CDs in their locked filing cabinets...
....or on hard disks with no backups....

And get them to put their data in a place where it'll be archived and looked after for the future properly.

So why data centres? Can't we just put everything in the cloud? Or on a webpage?

By David Fletcher
<http://www.cloudtweaks.com/2011/05/the-lighter-side-of-the-cloud-data-transfer/>

- Will you be able to find it again?
- How do you know it hasn't changed?
- How can someone else trust it?

Data preservation isn't enough

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n	⌈, ⌈, ⌈	⌈	⌈	⌈ ; H
p	⌈ ; H	*⌈ (⌈)	⌈, ⌈, ⌈	⌈ ; ⌈ ; ⌈
t	⌈ ; ⌈	⌈	⌈, ⌈	⌈ ; ⌈ ; ⌈
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L3 ⌈ (qa?) ; 43 ⌈, ⌈ (wa?) ; 65 ⌈ (ki?) ; 90 ⌈ (ka?)

filum of Linear A'

Phaistos Disk, 1700BC

The writers of these documents did a brilliant job of preserving for thousands of years the bits-and-bytes of their time!
But they've both been translated many times, and it's a shame the meanings are different.

Data Preservation is not enough, we need “Active Curation” to preserve Information

“publishing” on the web

To a scientist, there is little benefit from making their dataset available as a free download from a webpage.

Reputational risk of doing so:

- others might find errors, or
- take advantage of the dataset to earn new research funding

Even when sharing is mandated, there are simple ways of stopping people from using data openly posted on-line (e.g. incomprehensible filenames...)

There’s extra effort involved in preparing a dataset for use by others.

Data centres know this extra work is needed, and we want to make sure the dataset author gets credit!

How we're going to cite (and publish) data

We use digital object identifiers (DOIs) as part of our dataset citation because:

- They are actionable, interoperable, persistent links for (digital) objects
- Scientists are already used to citing papers using DOIs (and they trust them)
- There are moves by academic journal publishers (e.g. Nature) to require data sets to be cited in a stable way, i.e. using DOIs.
- The British Library and DataCite gave us an allocation of 500 DOIs to assign to datasets (we got to define what a dataset is).

The screenshot shows the homepage of the DOI System. The header includes the DOI logo, 'The DOI® System', and 'Developed by The International DOI Foundation (IDF)'. Navigation links for 'Search Guidelines', 'Contact Us', and 'Members Only' are present. A 'Site Search' box is on the left. The main content area features a 'Welcome to the DOI® System' section with introductory text about the system's purpose and management. Below this is an 'In the News' section with several news links. At the bottom, there is a 'Resolve a DOI Name' section with a text input field and a 'Submit' button. The footer contains copyright information and a 'Privacy Policy' link.

What sort of data can we/will we cite?

Dataset has to be:

- Stable (i.e. not going to be modified)
- Complete (i.e. not going to be updated)
- Permanent – by assigning a DOI we're committing to make the dataset available for posterity
- Good quality – by assigning a DOI we're giving it our data centre stamp of approval, saying that it's complete and all the metadata is available

When a dataset is cited that means:

- There will be bitwise fixity
- With no additions or deletions of files
- No changes to the directory structure in the dataset "bundle"

A DOI should point to a *html* representation of some record which describes a *data object* – i.e. a landing page.

Upgrades to versions of data formats will result in new editions of datasets.

What data centres can do and what we can't

Publishing data for the scholarly record

- Scientific journal publication mainly focuses on the analysis, interpretation and conclusions drawn from a given dataset.
- Examining the raw data that forms the dataset is more difficult, as datasets are usually stored in digital media, in a variety of (proprietary or non-standard) formats.
- Peer-review is generally only applied to the methodology and final conclusions of a piece of work, and not the underlying data itself. But if the conclusions are to stand, the data must be of good quality.
- A process of data publication, involving peer-review of datasets would be of benefit to many sectors of the academic community.

Most scientists regarded the new streamlined peer-review process as 'quite an improvement.'

<http://libguides.luc.edu/content.php?pid=5464&sid=164619>

(Scientific) Communication through the ages

Journals have been the traditional route for disseminating scientific knowledge. Papers work but...

...it's now becoming more important to ensure that the data that underpin a specific scientific result are available and that the conclusions arising from it can be tested.

If the data's lost/locked away/stored on obsolete media/in arcane formats/without documentation, how can we do that?

Technology has given us new tools, but it's also provided new challenges

<http://www.intoon.com/#68559>

“On-line journals are essentially paper journals, delivered by faster horses”, Jason Priem, DataCite Summer meeting 2011

Data journals and scientific publication of data

- Now we can cite our datasets using DOIs, we can give academic credit to those scientists who get cited – making them more likely to give us good quality data to archive.
- Publication – and scientific peer-review – is the next step
- We are working with the Royal Meteorological Society and Wiley-Blackwell to launch a new data journal in the next few months.
 - *Geoscience Data Journal (GDJ)* is an online-only, Open Access journal, publishing short data papers cross-linked to – and citing – datasets that have been deposited in approved data centres and awarded DOIs.

- Data journals already exist:
- Earth System Science Data (<http://earth-system-science-data.net/>)
- Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems (G3 <http://www.agu.org/journals/gc/>)

DATA: BY THE NUMBERS

Conclusions

- The NERC data citation and publication project has been running for over 1 year.
 - We're in phase 2 of the project (which will take 2 years)
 - At the end of this phase, all the NERC data centres will have:
 - At least 1 dataset with associated DOI
 - Guidelines for the data centre on what is an appropriate dataset to cite
 - Guidelines for data providers about data citation and the sort of datasets we will cite
- We've already had users coming to us requesting DOIs for their datasets.
- Publishers seem to be keen on developing data journals.

“We share because we do science, not alchemy.”

Jason Priem (Datacite Summer meeting, August 2011)

<http://www.keepcalm-omatic.co.uk/default.aspx#createposter>

Thanks!

Any questions?

Image credit: Borepatch <http://borepatch.blogspot.com/2010/06/its-not-what-you-dont-know-that-hurts.html>

A short digression: Citation vs. referencing

- Citation – data centre commitment regarding fixity, stability, permanence etc. of a dataset. Demonstrated by assignment of DOI
 - e.g. Darwin, Charles Robert. The Origin of Species. Vol. XI. The Harvard Classics. New York: P.F. Collier & Son, 1909–14;
- Referencing – no data centre commitment regarding fixity, stability, permanence etc. of a dataset. Dataset can still be referenced by URL – but link might be broken
 - e.g. Paragraph 3, page 42, Darwin, Charles Robert. The Origin of Species, 1859
- We want to be able to reference the individual part of the dataset (word/line/paragraph) without having to commit to assigning a DOI to everything but the dataset (book)
- If the dataset is properly frozen, then the reference to a part of it should work fine.
- People citing the dataset might want to reference a part of it, and we should make this possible. But we don't want to commit to DOI-ing every single bit of a dataset!
- And just because someone can (and will) reference something in a dataset that's not DOI-ready – this act should not trigger a DOI-citation

Journals – a 17th century technology

The first scientific journal, Journal des sçavans (later renamed Journal des savants), was first published on Monday, 5 January 1665.

It also carried a proportion of material that would not now be considered scientific, such as obituaries of famous men, church history, and legal reports.

It still exists, but is more of a literary journal

The first edition of the Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London was on 6 March 1665. That still exists, and continues to publish scientific information to this day.

Source gallica.bnf.fr / Bibliothèque nationale de France

Step XX: Get occasionally side-tracked searching for data specific comics on the internet

THE FOUR STAGES OF DATA LOSS DEALING WITH ACCIDENTAL DELETION OF MONTHS OF HARD-EARNED DATA

www.phdcomics.com

ICANNWASCHIEZBURGER.COM

Censormatic picture from:
http://scienceblogs.com/clock/2007/04/framing_politics_based_on_scie_1.php

